

Dr. Sivabalan Settu

Post Doctoral Fellow Lincoln University
College Malaysia

6G
Wireless Networking
Mobile Computing
Internet of Vehicle

	All	Since 2021
Citations	110	96
h-index	6	6
i10-index	4	3

TITLE	CITED BY	YEAR
Hybrid key generation for RSA and ECC E Vidhya, S Sivabalan, R Rathipriya 2019 International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems ...	17	2019
Ensemble learning for skin lesion classification: A robust approach for improved diagnostic accuracy (elslc) M Bhargavi, R Renugadevi, S Sivabalan, P Phani, J Ganesh, K Bhanu 2023 3rd International Conference on Innovative Mechanisms for Industry ...	13	2023
Biclustering using venus flytrap optimization algorithm R Gowri, S Sivabalan, R Rathipriya Computational Intelligence in Data Mining—Volume 1: Proceedings of the ...	12	2015
Arbitrary walk with minimum length based route identification scheme in graph structure for opportunistic wireless sensor network S Sivabalan, S Dhamodharavadhani, R Rathipriya Swarm intelligence for resource management in internet of things, 47-63	10	2020
Internet of Vehicle: effects of target tracking cluster routing in vehicle network S Kulanthaiyappan, S Settu, C Chellaih 2020 6th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication ...	9	2020
Opportunistic forward routing using bee colony optimization S Sivabalan, S Dhamodharavadhani, R Rathipriya Int J Comput Sci Eng 7 (5), 1820-1827	6	2019
Slot scheduling Mac using energy efficiency in ad hoc wireless networks S Sivabalan, R Rathipriya 2017 International Conference on Inventive Communication and Computational ...	6	2017
Optimizing energy efficient path selection using venus flytrap optimization algorithm in MANET S Sivabalan, R Gowri, R Rathipriya Computational Intelligence in Data Mining—Volume 1: Proceedings of the ...	6	2015
Artificial intelligence using federated learning: fundamentals, challenges, and applications AA Elngar, D Oliva, VE Balas CRC Press	5	2024
Predicting mental health through machine learning algorithms R Renugadevi, S Sivabalan 2023 9th International Conference on Smart Structures and Systems (ICSSS), 1-5	5	2023
Efficient Energy Resource Selection in Heterogeneous Sensor Networks using Non Swarm Intelligence Based Discrete Variable Search Optimization	5 [*]	2021

TITLE	CITED BY	YEAR
Algorithm S Settu, R Ramalingam		
Enhanced multi-hop routing for smart home network transmission S Sivabalan, R Rathipriya Journal of Analysis and Computation 14 (1), 1-12	5	2018
Energy Resource Optimization for Home Area Sensor Networks Using Discrete Venus Flytrap Algorithm R Ramalingam, S Settu International Journal of Applied Metaheuristic Computing (IJAMC) 12 (4), 47-61	3	2021
Analysis of Path selection policy of the Routing Protocols using Energy Efficient Metrics for Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks S Sivabalan, K Thangavel, S Sathish International Journal of Computational Intelligence and Informatics 3 (3 ...	3	2013
Smart Vehicles Zone Creation for Vehicle Ad Hoc Network S Kolandaiappan, C Chellaih, S Settu Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT) 12 (12 ...	2	2021
Revolutionizing agriculture through iot enhanced data analytics: A study from a blockchain technology perspective S Sivabalan, R Renugadevi, G Kalaiarasi, R Rathipriya, A Loganathan Blockchain-Enabled Internet of Things Applications in Healthcare: Current ...	1	2025
Federated learning-based smart transportation solutions: Deploying lightweight models on edge devices in the Internet of Vehicles S Settu, R Reddy, A Muralidhar, T Murugan, R Ramalingam Artificial Intelligence Using Federated Learning, 112-133	1	2024
Improving Software Quality: Realizing the Power of Software Design Patterns R Krishnan, KR Al Salmani, G Kalaiarasi, S Sivabalan Proceedings of Eighth International Conference on Information System Design ...	1	2024
Applied Artificial Intelligence: First International Conference, 2AI 2024, Solan, India, July 2–4, 2024, Proceedings R Hegadi, G Gupta, KC Santosh Springer Nature		2025
Cybersecurity and Data Management Innovations for Revolutionizing Healthcare T Murugan IGI Global		2024